

Ohio Small Town Sustainability Survey

Start of Block: Section I - Community Satisfaction

Q283

Q287 Welcome to the 2012 Ohio Small Town Sustainability Survey! We thank you for your interest in participating in the Ohio Small Town Sustainability Survey. As a reminder we ask that only one adult (age 18+) member of your household participate in the survey. Your household's participation in this survey is entirely voluntary and the information you provide will be used to help local organizations evaluate and better understand the opportunities and challenges in implementing local sustainability and energy use reduction initiatives in communities like yours. Please note that to continue to the survey you will need your RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the lower right-hand corner of the letter inviting you to participate. We thank you for taking the time to share your opinions and learn more about the survey. Sincerely, Thomas B. Cook Ph.D, M.P.H. Research Fellow for Community Evaluation Oberlin College To continue to the next screen please click in the button marked ">>" on the bottom left corner of each screen. If you should lose your internet connection or wish to resume the survey where you left off, simply return to www.townsurvey.org

Page Break

Q77 Please enter the **RESPONDENT ID*** as indicated on the letter inviting you to participate. Please note that on the following screen you will have the option of participating or declining participation in the survey.

Q124 * The RESPONDENT ID is located on the lower right-hand portion of the letter inviting you to participate which also included the link to this survey web-site. Please note that the RESPONDENT ID assures that the final survey results do not include any duplicate entries from the same person or household and also assures that the information you provide in this survey today will at no time be linked to any personal identifying information

Page Break

Information & Consent to Participate Please read carefully the following statements regarding your participation in this survey. If after reading through this page you have any additional questions about the nature or purpose of this survey or your participation, please see the contact information provided at the bottom of this page.

Statement of Purpose: The purpose of this community survey is to provide a baseline measure of residents' opinions, perceptions, attitudes and behaviors as they relate to local sustainability and energy use reduction initiatives.

Statement of the Scope and Nature of Participation: The survey which follows will ask you for your opinions about life in your community as well as you and your household's use of electricity and other resources. The survey will take between 10 to 15 minutes to complete.

Statement of Risks and Benefits of Participation: There are no experiments being done as part of this survey and there are no known risks or discomforts involved in your participation in this survey. There are also no direct benefits to you or your household for participation. There may be certain common benefits to the community as a whole by helping to improve the quality of information available to local organizations.

Statement of Participant Privacy & Confidentiality: Your responses to this survey will be strictly confidential and your contact information, identity, address, phone number and any other identifying information will not be disclosed in the reporting of the results nor will it be directly linked to your responses. At no time will anyone be provided access to individual responses to this survey which could be used to identify an individual respondent. All results from the survey will be reported for the entire community and never on an individual basis nor in a way that would possibly identify you or anyone in your household.

Statement of Volunteer Nature of Participation: Your participation in this survey is strictly voluntary and declining participation or stopping participation at any time does not imply any form of penalty or loss of benefits, nor will it impact the delivery, quantity, quality or cost of any city services or utilities. Your household will be eligible to participate in future years of the survey even if you decline participation this year.

Statement of Participant Selection Procedures & Purpose for Random Selection: Your household was randomly selected to participate in this survey based on a list of all residential addresses in your city. Unlike a Census which collects information from all households, the community survey is designed to get a representative sample of your city's population. This random selection process is essential to assure that the responses collected reflect the "average" responses of all community members and not just those who are most interested in participating.

Statement of Eligibility You must be a 18 years of age or over to participate in this community survey. **Contact Information:** If you should have any question about your participation in this survey, please contact Dr. Thomas Cook, Research Fellow for Community Evaluation at 440-785-0823 or tcook@oberlin.edu or Heather Hogan, Chair of the Institutional Review Board at (440) 775-8410 or heather.hogan@oberlin.edu.

I hereby confirm that I am 18 years of age or older and have read and understood the statements and instructions above and give my consent to participate in the Ohio Small Town Sustainability Survey. (1)

I would like to decline participation on behalf of myself and my household. (2)

Skip To: End of Survey If Q113 = I would like to decline participation on behalf of myself and my household.

Page Break

Q260 Please confirm that you are a current resident of city listed below by selecting the circle next to that city name.

Display This Choice:

If If Please enter the RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the ... Text Response Is Contains A*

Oberlin (1)

Display This Choice:

If If Please enter the RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the ... Text Response Is Contains B*

Berea (2)

Page Break

Q284 COMMUNITY SATISFACTION The first few questions are about your overall satisfaction with life in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$. Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement. Please note that throughout the survey " $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ " refers to the City of $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$.

Page Break

Q1 Overall, how satisfied are you with life in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}?

- Very Satisfied (1)
- Satisfied (2)
- Neutral (3)
- Dissatisfied (4)
- Very Dissatisfied (5)

Page Break

Q2 When thinking about life in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$, how satisfied are you with each of the following?

	Very Satisfied (1)	Satisfied (2)	Neutral (3)	Dissatisfied (4)	Very Dissatisfied (5)
Retail and shopping opportunities (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Employment opportunities (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Arts, entertainment, and cultural opportunities (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Community events and festivals (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
Local government (5)	<input type="radio"/>				
Public spaces (6)	<input type="radio"/>				
Opportunities for safe biking and walking (7)	<input type="radio"/>				
Parks and recreation opportunities (8)	<input type="radio"/>				
Public transportation (9)	<input type="radio"/>				
Public schools (10)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q156 CITY SERVICES

Q120 How would you rate each of the following City of [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) services in terms of cost?

	Very Good (1)	Good (2)	Average (3)	Poor (4)	Very Poor (5)
Electric service (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Water & Sewer (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Garbage collection (3)	<input type="radio"/>				

Page Break

Q132 COMMUNITY LIFE

You will now be provided a series of statements about life in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#). Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement.

Page Break

Q3 I feel I belong in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#).

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q133 Overall, I think $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ is a good environment to raise children.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q134 The \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community is respectful and accepting of people who have differing religious and spiritual beliefs.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q137 I am happy to live in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q136 The \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community is respectful and accepting of people with different racial and ethnic backgrounds.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q138 The \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community is respectful and accepting of people with different political opinions.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q141 Despite our differences, we can commit ourselves to common community goals.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q142 If people in the community were planning something, I would feel that it is something WE are doing as opposed to something THEY are doing.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q146 Most people in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} can be trusted.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q147 I feel like a valued and valuable member of the [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) community.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q148 I have an understanding of how and why things happen the way they do in
\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q149 I can help make things happen or help to change things if I need to in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#).

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q184 I often visit with neighbors inside their homes.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q185 I often stop and talk with people in my neighborhood.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q186 I believe my neighbors would help me in an emergency.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q260 = Oberlin

Q143 The residents of Oberlin and the College of Oberlin act as one community.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Q260 = Berea

Q285 The residents of Berea and Baldwin Wallace College act as one community.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q290 The local college and city work together to improve the community.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q160 COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION

Q59 Below is a list of activities and organizations that some people in your community participate in. Please indicate how often you participated in each of the following activities over the past year.

	Never (1)	Once a Year or Less (2)	Several Times a Year (3)	Once a Month (4)	2-3 Times a Month (5)	Once a Week (6)
Attended a public meeting or council meeting (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Worked with other community members to solve a community problem (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Attended church or religious services or activities of faith-based organization (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participated in a PTA/PTO or other K-12 school-based organization (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Voted in local elections (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q161 **COMMUNITY SAFETY**

Q17 How safe would you feel walking alone *during the day...*

	Very Safe (1)	Safe (2)	Neutral (3)	Unsafe (4)	Very Unsafe (5)
...in your neighborhood? (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
...in the park closest to you? (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
...in the downtown or business district of \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}? (3)	<input type="radio"/>				

Page Break

Q101 How safe would you feel walking alone *at night*...

	Very Safe (1)	Safe (2)	Neutral (3)	Unsafe (4)	Very Unsafe (5)
...in your neighborhood? (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
...in the park closest to you? (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
...in the downtown or business district of \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}? (3)	<input type="radio"/>				

Page Break

Q163 QUALITY OF LIFE AND COST OF LIVING

Q19 Below are some questions about the overall quality of life and cost of living in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$.

	Very Good (1)	Good (2)	Average (3)	Bad (4)	Very Bad (5)
Overall, how would you rate $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ as a place for shopping, recreation, working, and living? (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Overall, how do you rate $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ as a place to earn an income or do business? (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Overall, how would you rate the cost of living in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$? (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Compared to the cost of living in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ two years ago, how would you rate the cost of living in $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ now? (4)	<input type="radio"/>				

Page Break

End of Block: Section I - Community Satisfaction

Start of Block: Section II - Energy, Recycling and Water Use

Page Break

Q151 RECYCLING The following statements are about recycling in
\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}. Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with
each statement.

Page Break

Q247 There are resources in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) to help me recycle.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q248 I have taken on a leadership role in promoting recycling in my community.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q249 I believe that the items put in recycling bins are actually being recycled.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q250 It is easy for me to be consistent about recycling in
\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q204 How often do you think residents of \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} recycle?

- Very Often (1)
- Often (2)
- Sometimes (3)
- Rarely (4)
- Never (5)

Page Break

Q261 How often do you recycle consumer packaging and containers such as cardboard, plastic and glass?

- Always (1)
- Very often (2)
- Often (3)
- Sometimes (4)
- Rarely or Never (5)

Page Break

Q177 What do you do with yard waste materials?

- Compost in my own yard (1)
- Put curbside for city pick-up (2)
- Bag it for trash pick-up (3)
- I do not have a yard (4)

Page Break

Q152 ENERGY USE The following statements are about energy use in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#). Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement.

Page Break

Q187 I feel the [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) community supports efforts to reduce household energy consumption and save on household energy costs.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q208 There are programs and resources in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} to help me reduce my household energy consumption and costs.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q209 There is someone in my community who can give advice or support to help reduce my household energy consumption and costs.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q210 I believe that as a community we can work together to reduce our total energy consumption.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q207 I often think about electricity consumption when I turn a light or appliance on or off.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q189 I consciously make decisions to minimize my electricity use.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q189 = Strongly Agree

Or Q189 = Agree

Or Q189 = Neither Agree nor Disagree

Q190 I consciously make decisions to minimize other people's electricity use in my household.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q191 I have relatively little ability to influence electricity consumption in my household.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q202 How often do you think residents of $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ try to conserve energy?

- Very Often (1)
- Often (2)
- Sometimes (3)
- Rarely (4)
- Never (5)

Page Break

Q11 During a typical winter, at what temperature in degrees Fahrenheit do you generally keep the thermostat when at home?

- 60-65 F (1)
- 66-67 F (2)
- 68-69 F (3)
- 70-71 F (4)
- 72-73 F (5)
- 74-75 F (6)
- 76-77 F (7)
- 78 F or Higher (8)

Page Break

Q192 Do you have and use a programmable thermostat?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - Not sure (3)
-

Display This Question:

If Q192 = Yes

Q266 Do you use the programmable thermostat to adjust the temperature of your home when you are away from home or asleep?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - Sometimes (3)
-

Page Break

Q62 Below are some types of improvements or actions some people take to reduce consumption of energy in their home. Please indicate whether you or someone else in your household or a landlord have taken these steps in the past 5 years.

	Yes (1)	No (2)	Not Sure (3)
Installed energy-efficient windows (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Installed new insulation to reduce heating costs (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Installed energy-efficient appliances (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other home improvements to reduce energy consumption (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Q168 What percentage of the light bulbs in your home are energy-efficient (compact fluorescent or LED)?

- None (1)
- Less than 25% (6)
- Between 25% - 50% (2)
- Between 50% - 75% (3)
- Over 75% (4)

Page Break

Q173 How often do you use line-drying instead of an electric or gas clothes dryer?

- Always (1)
- Very Often (2)
- Often (3)
- Sometimes (4)
- Rarely or Never (5)

Page Break

Q193 Have you installed timers or motion sensors on lights or other automatic devices to reduce electricity use and costs?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Not Sure (3)

Page Break

Q71 Do you have air conditioning where you live?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Display This Question:

If Q71 = Yes

Q70 In the summer months, how warm would it have to be inside your home based on the thermostat for you to turn on the air conditioning?

- 65-67 F (1)
- 68-69 F (2)
- 70-71 F (3)
- 72-73 F (4)
- 74-75 F (5)
- 76-77 F (6)
- 78-79 F (7)
- 80-81F (8)
- 82-83F (9)
- 84-85F (10)
- > 85F (11)
- I would not use air conditioning regardless of temperature (12)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q71 = Yes

Q88 About how many days during a typical summer do you use air conditioning?

- Every day (1)
- Most days (2)
- At least every other day (3)
- Some days (4)
- Only when it is extremely hot (5)
- Not at all (6)

Page Break

Q253 WATER USE & WATER QUALITY The following statements are about water use, the environment and water quality in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#). Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement.

Page Break

Q212 The \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community supports efforts to preserve water quality in creek, rivers, and lakes.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q280 I believe that as a community we can work together to improve water quality in creeks, rivers, and lakes.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q216 I often think about water consumption when I am taking a shower, flushing the toilet, washing my hands or using water in other ways.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q218 I consciously make decisions to minimize the amount of water I use.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q218 = Neither Agree nor Disagree

Or Q218 = Agree

And Q218 = Strongly Agree

Q219 I consciously make decisions to minimize the amount of water other people in my household use.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q220 I have relatively little ability to influence local water quality in creeks, rivers, and lakes.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q221 I have relatively little ability to influence water consumption in my household.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q223 My water use has an important impact on the environment.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q214 I often feel a strong connection to nature.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q174 Have you or someone else installed a low-flow toilet in your home?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Not Sure (3)

Page Break

Q175 Have you or someone else installed a low-flow showerhead in your home?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Not Sure (3)

Page Break

Q176 Do you have a rain barrel for collecting water run-off from your gutters?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Not Sure (3)

Page Break

Q12 When taking a shower, about how long do you usually take in minutes?

- Less than 5 minutes (1)
- 5 - 10 minutes (2)
- 10 - 15 minutes (3)
- 15 - 20 minutes (4)
- More than 20 minutes (5)

Page Break

Q254 TRANSPORTATION OPTIONS The following statements are about transportation options in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) including public transit, walking and biking. Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement.

Page Break

Q224 The \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community supports efforts to bicycle and walk.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q225 I believe that as a community we can work together to reduce automobile use in town.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q226 It is easy for me to bike or walk to places I would like to go in
\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q255 It is easy for me to use public transportation to go places I would like to go.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q205 How often do residents of [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) ride bikes or walk to get around town?

- Very Often (1)
- Often (2)
- Sometimes (3)
- Rarely (4)
- Never (5)

Page Break

End of Block: Section II - Energy, Recycling and Water Use

Start of Block: Section III - Local Food and Food Access

Q122 ACCESS TO FOOD & LOCAL FOOD PRODUCTION

The following questions are about the availability of food and your opinions about locally produced foods.

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Q228 I can easily find foods in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) that I consider healthy.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q227 How often do you drive outside of \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} to find the groceries that you want?

- more than once a week (1)
- once a week (2)
- two or three times a month (3)
- monthly (4)
- rarely (5)

Page Break

Q234 I can easily find information on farmers' markets and where to find locally grown foods in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#).

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q235 I find that locally grown foods tend to be more expensive than non-locally grown foods.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q229 I can easily purchase fresh fruits and vegetables in
\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q230 Do you raise any of your own food?

Yes (1)

No (3)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q230 = Yes

Q267 What kinds of food do you raise? Please check all that apply.

- Berries (e.g., strawberries) (1)
- Fruit (e.g., apples) (2)
- Herbs (e.g. basil) (3)
- Vegetables (e.g. tomatoes) (4)
- Eggs (5)
- Meat and/or dairy (6)

Display This Question:

If Q267 = Vegetables (e.g. tomatoes)

Q268 Roughly what percentage of the vegetables you eat do you grow yourself?

- Less than 25% (1)
- Between 25% - 50% (2)
- Between 50% - 75% (3)
- Over 75% (4)

Page Break

Q270 Do you preserve any food to eat at a later time?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q270 = Yes

Q271 What preservation methods do you use? Check all that apply.

- Canning (1)
- Drying (2)
- Fermentation (3)
- Freezing (4)
- Packing in oil (5)
- Storing in cool place (6)

Page Break

Q251 How many of the meals that you eat at home use unprocessed (e.g. fresh produce) or minimally processed (e.g. pasta) ingredients?

- All meals (1)
- Most Meals (2)
- Some Meals (3)
- A Few Meals (4)
- Almost No Meals (5)

Page Break

Q15 When shopping for food, please indicate how important each of the following factors is in determining what you purchase.

	Extremely Important (1)	Very Important (2)	Somewhat Important (3)	Not That Important (4)	Not At All Important (5)
The food is locally grown or produced. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The food is organic. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Whether the food is unprocessed. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
That meat is raised in a humane manner (leave blank if you don't eat meat). (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is convenient to prepare. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
You know the person or people that produced it. (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The food item is the most affordable of its kind. (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

End of Block: Section III - Local Food and Food Access

Start of Block: Section V - Local Economy and Development

Q252 LOCAL ECONOMY & BUSINESS CLIMATE The following statements are about the local business climate in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#). Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement.

Page Break

Q236 The \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} community supports our local businesses by shopping locally.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q237 [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) businesses are an important source of jobs for local residents.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q281 I have a friend or neighbor who works for a business in
\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q240 As a community we can work together to improve the local economy regardless of what happens elsewhere.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q241 [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) offers the types of restaurants that I prefer.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q244 [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) offers the types of businesses and shops that I prefer.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q245 The town of \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} is well-suited to my tastes.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q257 I believe [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) can be a destination for regional tourism.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly Disagree (5)

Page Break

Q289 How do you feel the local college positively or negatively impacts the community in each of the following areas?

	Negatively (1)	Somewhat Negatively (2)	Neutral (3)	Somewhat Positively (4)	Positively (5)
Local businesses (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Local schools (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
City government and politics (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Community safety (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Community non-profit organizations (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Arts, culture and events (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Downtown and other public spaces (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Neighborhood quality of life (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Section V - Local Economy and Development

Start of Block: Section VI - Opinion

Page Break

Q21 How important is it that each of the following types of buildings are renovated to reduce energy use and waste?

	Extremely Important (1)	Very Important (2)	Somewhat Important (3)	Not Very Important (4)	Not At All Important (5)
The public library (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The public schools (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Government buildings such as City Hall (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
College buildings (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Local businesses (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Individual homes (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

End of Block: Section VI - Opinion

Start of Block: Section VII - Personal Behavior and Demographic Characteristics

Page Break

Q54 Overall how motivated are you to do each of the following activities?

	Highly Motivated (1)	Motivated (2)	Somewhat motivated (3)	Only slightly motivated (4)	Not at all motivated (5)
Conserve energy (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bike or walk for transportation (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reduce water use (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improve water quality (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Purchase local foods (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Recycle (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Compost (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Invest money locally (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bike, walk or run for exercise (11)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Eat healthy foods (12)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q54 [Conserve energy] <= 3

Q91 In thinking about your sources of motivation to conserve energy, how important would you say each of the following are as a source of motivation.

	Very Important (1)	Important (2)	Somewhat Important (3)	Not that Important (4)	Not at all important (5)
My neighbors and friends (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Local initiatives or community leaders (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My children or other family members (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Climate change (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improving the quality of the local environment (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improving the quality of the environment for future generations (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My economic well-being (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The economic health of \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The economic health of the US (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q54 [Conserve energy] <= 4

Q275 Please indicate how certain you are that you can carry out your intentions to reduce energy use. I can carry out my plans to reduce my household energy use....

	Very Certain (1)	Certain (2)	Neutral (3)	Uncertain (4)	Very Uncertain (5)
...even when it requires a lot of conscious effort on my part. (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even when my comfort seems more important than conserving energy when it is very cold or very hot. (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even if I do not receive a great deal of support from others in my household. (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even if I have to keep records or track how much energy I am using. (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even if sometimes it does not feel it is making much of a difference in my energy bills. (5)	<input type="radio"/>				

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q54 [Bike or walk for transportation] <= 4

Q276 Please indicate how certain you are that you can carry out your intentions to bike or walk for transportation. For short trips, I can carry out my plans to walk or bike rather than drive....

	Very Certain (1)	Certain (2)	Neutral (3)	Uncertain (4)	Very Uncertain (5)
...even when the weather is not favorable for walking or biking. (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even when I do not feel I have as much time as usual. (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even if I do not see many others in my neighborhood doing it. (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even if sometimes it feels like a lot of extra effort. (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even if I need to carry several things with me either coming or going. (5)	<input type="radio"/>				

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q54 [Recycle] <= 4

Q277 Please indicate how certain you are that you can carry out your intentions to recycle. I can carry out my intentions regarding recycling...

	Very Certain (1)	Certain (2)	Neutral (3)	Uncertain (4)	Very Uncertain (5)
...even when I have too much to do. (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even when it is not convenient or I have to go out of my way. (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even if it requires a lot of extra effort. (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even when others around me are not doing the same. (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even when I am in a hurry. (5)	<input type="radio"/>				

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q54 [Bike, walk or run for exercise] <= 4

Q278 Please indicate how certain you are that you can carry out your intentions to pursue your physical fitness and exercise intentions. I can manage to carry out my physical fitness and exercise intentions....

	Very Certain (1)	Certain (2)	Neutral (3)	Uncertain (4)	Very Uncertain (5)
... even when I have worries or problems. (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even if I feel depressed. (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even when I feel tense. (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even when I am tired. (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even when I am busy. (5)	<input type="radio"/>				

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q54 [Eat healthy foods] <= 4

Q279 Please indicate how certain you are that you can carry out your intentions to eat healthier foods. I can manage to stick to healthful foods..

	Very Certain (1)	Certain (2)	Neutral (3)	Uncertain (4)	Very Uncertain (5)
...even if I need a long time to develop the necessary routines. (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even if I have to try several times or do different things until it works. (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even if I do not receive a great deal of support from others when making my first attempts. (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even if I have to make a detailed plan. (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
... even when I am busy. (5)	<input type="radio"/>				

Page Break

Q258 DEMOGRAPHICS The following demographic questions are for statistical purposes only and to help assure that the responses we receive are representative of the general population.

Q39 What is your age (in years)?

Q40 What is your sex?

Male (1)

Female (2)

Q42 Are you either Hispanic or Latino?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Q41 What is your race?

- American Indian or Alaska Native (1)
- Asian (2)
- Black or African American (3)
- Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander (4)
- White (5)
- Mixed race (6)
- Other (7)

Page Break

Q74 How long have you lived in \${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}?

- < 1 year (1)
- 1-2 years (2)
- 3-4 years (3)
- 5-10 years (4)
- > 10 years (5)

Page Break

Q96 What would you estimate as your total household income per year?

- < \$20,000 (1)
- \$20,000 - \$39,999 (2)
- \$40,000 - \$59,999 (3)
- \$60,000 - \$79,999 (4)
- \$80,000 - \$99,999 (5)
- \$100,000 + (6)
- I do not wish to share this information (7)

Page Break

Q43 Please tell us a little about who lives in your home. For each of the following, please indicate how many people in each category live in your home.

Older Adults > Age 70 (1) _____

Adults ages 30-70 (2) _____

Young adults ages 18-29 (3) _____

Teens (12-18) (4) _____

Children ages 5-11 (5) _____

Preschoolers ages 0-4 (6) _____

Page Break _____

Q47 What type of residence do you live in?

- Apartment (1)
- Condominium (2)
- House (3)
- Other (4)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q47 = House

Or Q47 = Condominium

Or Q47 = Other

Q52 Do you (or other people who live with you) own your home?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Page Break

Q63 Do you own or lease a motor vehicle or have regular access to a motor vehicle?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Skip To: Q67 If Q63 = No

Page Break

Q65 For the vehicle you drive the most often, what would you estimate as the vehicle's typical miles per gallon?

- < 10 MPG (1)
- 10-15 MPG (2)
- 16-20 MPG (3)
- 21-25 MPG (4)
- 26-30 MPG (5)
- 31-35 MPG (6)
- 36-40 MPG (7)
- > 40 MPG (8)

Page Break

Q66 In a typical year, about how many miles do you drive?

- Less than 5,000 (1)
- 5,000-7,499 (2)
- 7,500-9,999 (3)
- 10,000-12,499 (4)
- 12,500-14,999 (5)
- 15,000-19,999 (6)
- 20,000-24,999 (7)
- 25,000-29,999 (8)
- 30,000 or more (9)

Page Break

Q67 Do you currently work either full-time or part-time?

- Yes, I work full-time (1)
- Yes, I work part-time (2)
- No, I am not currently working (3)

Skip To: Q73 If Q67 = No, I am not currently working

Q68 How many miles do you travel to work in each direction? That is, how far is it in miles from where you live from where you work?

- 0 to 1 Mile (1)
- 2-3 Miles (2)
- 4-5 Miles (3)
- 6-10 Miles (4)
- 11-15 Miles (5)
- 16-20 Miles (6)
- 21-25 Miles (7)
- 26-30 Miles (8)
- 31-35 Miles (9)
- 36-40 Miles (10)
- > 40 Miles (11)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q68 = > 40 Miles

Q69 How many miles do you typically drive to work each way?

Page Break

Q72 In the past 7 days, what was your primary form of transportation to get to and from work?

- Drove alone (1)
- Carpool (2)
- Public transit (3)
- Walking (4)
- Biking (5)

Page Break

Q292 How often are you required or do you feel obligated to work more than 40 hours per week at your primary job?

- Every week (1)
- Often (2)
- Sometimes (3)
- Rarely (4)
- Never (5)

Page Break

Q73 In the past 7 days, what was your primary form of transportation for all trips including shopping, running errands and work?

- Drove alone (1)
- Carpool (2)
- Public transit (3)
- Walking (4)
- Biking (5)

Page Break

Q60 Below is a list of local sources of information some people use to get information about things happening in [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#). For each source listed below, please indicate how often you get information from that source about [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#).

	Never (1)	Once a Year or Less (2)	Several Times a Year (3)	Once a Month (4)	2-3 Times a Month (5)	Once a Week (6)	2-3 Times a Week (7)	4-6 Times a Week (8)	Daily (9)
Local-access cable television channel (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Local newspaper (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Community newsletters (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
School newsletters (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Local college publications (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bulletin boards in local businesses and public buildings (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electronic or digital display boards (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Local community organization websites (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
City website (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

College
website (10)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Q260 = Oberlin

Q79 Before concluding this survey, we want to make sure that all residents of the City of [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) are equally represented in this survey. Shown below is a Google map of City of [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) where the pin marked "A" marks the geographic center of town. Please indicate on the map below the approximate location of where you live within [\\${Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}](#) by clicking on that location on the map below. If you prefer not to indicate approximately where you live or cannot find your location on the map, simply select a location or landmark on the map which is in the general direction of where you live relative to the pin marked "A".

Display This Question:

If Q260 = Berea

Q286 Before concluding this survey, we want to make sure that all residents of the City of $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ are equally represented in this survey. Shown below is a Google map of City of $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ where the pin marked "A" marks the geographic center of town. Please indicate on the map below the approximate location of where you live within $\{Q260/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$ by clicking on that location on the map below. If you prefer not to indicate approximately where you live or cannot find your location on the map, simply select a location or landmark on the map which is in the general direction of where you live relative to the pin marked "A".

Display This Question:

If If Please enter the RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the ... Text Response Is Equal to A2012109*

Or Or Please enter the RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the ... Text Response Is Equal to B2012109*

Or Or Please enter the RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the ... Text Response Is Equal to a2012109*

Or Or Please enter the RESPONDENT ID as indicated on the ... Text Response Is Equal to b2012109*

Q293 Based on the RESPONDENT ID you provided, you entered a general code for your city based on a reminder card delivered to your address. To help avoid any possible duplicate responses in the survey results, please do one of the following: 1) Enter the numeric portion of your street address in the box below. For example, if you live at 1005 Maple St., you would enter "1005". If you live at 3 Maple Street you would just enter the number "3" in the box below. OR 2) If you have the original letter inviting you to participate with your original RESPONDENT ID, please enter that RESPONDENT ID (e.g. "A101001") in the box below.

Page Break

